

METHODS OF ANALYSIS OF SUBSTANCES SYNTHESIZED VIA ETHYLENE TELOMERIZATION REACTION

S.Z.Khudayberganova

Sh.Y.Bolibekova

A.G.Kalibekova

Tashkent State Technical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15718610>

Annotation

This scientific work explores the synthesis of isopropyl and isoamyl alcohols via telomerization of ethylene with methanol under high-pressure hermetic reactor conditions. Various analytical methods including IR spectroscopy, chromatographic-mass spectrometry, Raman spectroscopy, physicochemical, quantum chemical, and mathematical modeling were used to study and identify the structure and properties of the synthesized compounds. The analysis included the determination of boiling point, density, refractive index, and molecular refraction. IR spectra were obtained using the “INVENIO-S FTIR” spectrometer, and Raman spectra were recorded with the “InVia Raman BRAVO” device. Chromato-mass analysis was conducted using the Agilent MSD 5975C-GC7890A spectrometer. Quantum chemical calculations were performed via HyperChem Professional software, while mathematical modeling and experimental data processing were conducted using Maple 2018, applying the method of least squares. Density was determined using pycnometers, and refractive indices were measured by an Abbe refractometer.

Keywords

Ethylene telomerization, isopropyl alcohol, isoamyl alcohol, IR spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, chromatographic-mass spectrometry, quantum chemical modeling, mathematical modeling, refractive index, molecular refraction, physical properties.

In the scientific research, IR spectroscopy, chromatographic-mass spectrometry, Raman spectroscopy, physicochemical, quantum chemical, and mathematical modeling methods were used. The structure and composition of the products obtained through chemical synthesis processes were studied and analyzed. Chromatographic-mass spectra were obtained in the liquid phase using a standard HP-5MS column on an “Agilent MSD 5975C-GC7890A” chromatograph-mass spectrometer, operating in the temperature range from 0 °C to 320 °C, with initial heating from 50 °C to 120 °C. In the chromatographic-mass spectrum of the synthesized isopropanol, ions corresponding to the

molecular mass of the compound and fragment ions resulting from decomposition were identified.

The IR spectra of the synthesized compounds were obtained using the “INVENIO-S FTIR” spectrometer, manufactured by Bruker in 2021, which has an optical spectral resolution of less than 0.25 cm^{-1} and operates within the IR spectral range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The Raman spectra of the compounds were recorded using the “InVia Raman spectrometer BRAVO.” This spectrometer is particularly suitable for identifying specific features of compounds, such as molecular “fingerprints,” and for observing the state, tension, and deformation changes in molecular bonds. During analysis, the laser beam was focused on sample areas with a diameter of $10\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to determine volume.

Quantum chemical calculations are among the physicochemical research methods used to evaluate the geometry of molecules, calculate the stability of intermediates and transition states, and determine the properties of complex organic compounds. The chemical properties and reactivity of molecules depend on their electronic structure and energetic characteristics. Within the scope of the dissertation, quantum chemical calculations were conducted using the “HyperChem Professional” software to study the formation energy, total energy, heat of formation, electronic energy, electron density distribution, nuclear energy, dipole moment, and possible reaction pathways of both the initial and synthesized substances.

Mathematical modeling of the process and processing of experimental data – Mathematical modeling and data processing methods make it possible to identify chemical reaction processes in a short time and optimize them, enabling modern design with minimal cost and time. The synthesis processes of isopropyl and isoamyl alcohols were mathematically modeled and their experimental data processed using the least squares method in the Maple 2018 software.

Determination of density. In chemical industry laboratories and pharmaceutical plants, pycnometers are typically used along with hydrometers for technical analyses. Density is one of the indicators used in various industrial facilities to determine the quality of liquid substances. It helps verify whether the properties of raw materials and finished products comply with established standards.

Before starting the analysis with the pycnometer, it was thoroughly rinsed with a chromic acid mixture, followed by distilled water. First, the clean and dry pycnometer was weighed on an analytical balance. Then, both the glass vessel

and distilled water were heated to the same temperature at which the density of the studied liquid was to be measured. The distilled water was poured into the empty pycnometer up to the calibration mark on its neck. After that, the mass of the pycnometer with water was measured. Then, the water was poured out, and the measuring device was dried in a special oven. Isopropyl alcohol was poured into the prepared glass vessel up to the same calibration mark. The temperature was kept identical to that during the water filling. Finally, the pycnometer was weighed again.

The density of isoamyl alcohol was also determined using the same method by measuring the masses of the pycnometer filled with water and the pycnometer filled with isoamyl alcohol.

In the final stage, calculations were performed using the following formula. Given that the density of water at 20 °C is 0.9982 g/cm³, the relative density is calculated using the formula below:

$$d_4^{20} = \frac{m}{W} * 0,998230$$

m – the mass of the substance in the pycnometer at 20 °C;
 W – the mass of an equal volume of water at the same temperature (20 °C).

Boiling point. The boiling point of liquid organic compounds is used to determine their purity and to separate them. This can be performed using a distillation apparatus. For the distillation, 75 ml of isopropyl alcohol was poured into a 100 ml flask equipped with a thermometer and heated on an electric heater.

Boiling point of isopropanol: $T_{\text{boil}}(\text{isopropanol}) = 82.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
The boiling point of isoamyl alcohol was determined using the same method:
 $T_{\text{boil}}(\text{isoamyl alcohol}) = 132 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Refractive Index and Molecular Refraction. These properties are used to determine the purity of liquid compounds. The change in direction of light as it passes from one medium to another is called refraction. The incident ray, the refracted ray, and the perpendicular drawn to the point of incidence at the boundary of the two media lie in the same plane. If the angle of incidence is denoted by α and the angle of refraction by β , then the ratio of the sine of the angle of incidence to the sine of the angle of refraction is a constant value for the two media:

$$\sin \alpha / \sin \beta = C_1 / C_2 = n$$

C_1 and C_2 are the speeds of light in the first and second media respectively;
 n is the constant for the two media and is called the refractive index.

Air is usually considered as the first medium. The refractive index depends on temperature and dispersion. An increase in temperature by 1 °C typically reduces the refractive index by approximately 0.0004. The refractive indices of the synthesized organic compounds were determined using an Abbe refractometer.

Procedure for measurement: First, the prism block is opened, then a drop of the liquid sample is placed on the lower prism using a pipette, after which the prism block is closed. The refractometer is positioned so that adequate light falls on the viewing area. The main adjustment screw is turned until part of the visual field becomes dark. The compensator of the refractometer is adjusted until the boundary line is clearly visible and aligns precisely with the central crosshairs in the eyepiece. The reading shown on the refractometer scale is recorded. To verify the reliability of the measurement, the process is repeated several times. The surfaces of the refractometer prisms are first cleaned with a damp cloth and then dried with cotton.

After determining the refractive indices and densities of the substances, the molecular refraction (R_M) values are calculated using the Lorentz-Lorenz formula.

$$R_M = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 1} \cdot \frac{M}{d}$$

M – molecular weight;

d – density of the substance.

Molecular (or specific) refraction represents the polarizability of all electrons in a molecule. Molecular refraction does not depend on temperature, pressure, or the physical state (phase) of the substance. Refraction is considered an additive physical property, meaning that the molecular refraction of a compound is equal to the sum of the refractions of the atoms that constitute the molecule.

The methods for synthesizing isopropyl and isoamyl alcohols via the telomerization reaction of ethylene with methanol are presented. The synthesis was conducted in a hermetically sealed reactor operating under high pressure. Methods for determining the physical properties—such as boiling point, density, refractive index, and molecular refraction—of the synthesized compounds are provided. To determine the molecular structure of the synthesized compounds, Raman spectroscopy, IR spectroscopy, and chromatographic-mass spectrometry methods were used. For mathematical modeling of the process and analysis of experimental data, the Maple 2018 software was applied.

References:

1. T. A. Faßbach, A. J. Vorholt, W. Leitner. The Telomerization of 1,3-Dienes-A Reaction Grows Up // Journal Of Molecular Catalysis, 2019, Volume 11(4). – pp. 1153-1166.
2. Dmitry S. Suslov, Mikhail V. Bykov, Marina V. Belova, Pavel A. Abramov, Vitaly S. Tkach. Palladium(II)-acetylacetonate complexes containing phosphine and diphosphine ligands and their catalytic activities in telomerization of 1,3-dienes with diethylamine // Journal of Organometallic Chemistry, 2014, Volume 752. – pp. 37-44.
3. Peter J. C. Hausoul, Sinedu D. Tefera, Jelle Blekxtoon, Pieter C. A. Bruijninx, Robertus J. M. Klein Gebbink, Bert M. Weckhuysen. Pd/TOMPP-catalysed telomerisation of 1,3-butadiene with lignin-type phenols and thermal Claisen rearrangement of linear telomers // Catal. Sci. Technol, 2013, Volume 3(5). – pp. 1215-1223.

